

SOME ASPECTS OF EDUCATIONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES

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The problem of ecology is relevant even in all corners of the earth's surface. Only the degree of its tension in different countries and regions of the world is characteristic. According to the same, one of the most dangerous environmental disaster zones has emerged in the Central Asian region, namely. "The complexity of the situation lies in the fact that it is caused not only by the denial of this problem for several decades, but also by the fact that almost all spheres of human activity in the region are under threat to the environment. We must not allow nature to be treated in the plural and arrogantly. We have bitter experience in this regard. Nature does not forgive such an attitude." [1] the false socialist ideological claim that a cell uniting people by nature has become a tragedy, especially for the lives of many people, one people and the nations of the Central Asian miptag.

Extreme salinity of the land is a huge environmental problem for Uzbekistan. Over the past 50 years, the area of irrigated land has increased by almost 2 million hectares, of which about 1 million hectares have become unsuitable for irrigation.

Soil pollution by various industrial and household waste is a real disaster for a generation. Gross violation of the rules of storage, transportation and use of various chemicals, harmful substances and mineral fertilizers, industrial and construction materials leads to pollution of the Earth. In limiting the possibilities of its effective use.

The tension on the islands is one of the largest environmental and humanitarian tragedies in human history. Almost 35 million people living in the marine basin are still under its influence.

For 20-25 years, we have not witnessed the contamination of one of the largest closed reservoirs in the world. However, before the eyes of an entire generation, the Khol-Khali, which lost an entire sea, never happened. Due to the drying up of the island sea, a complex set of environmental, socio-economic and demographic problems of an international, large-scale nature has arisen. The appearance of dust and salt storms, the transformation of land into a desert, climate and landscape changes not only on the island, but also in barren areas far beyond the borders of the Kyrgyz Republic - these are the consequences of this tragedy.

Such an environmental situation could not have serious consequences. Dust storms have become more frequent in recent years, accompanied by severe droughts and other environmental disasters. For example, a severe drought in the region in 2000 resulted in the loss of crops on an area of 210,000 hectares, or 45% of all arable land, due to drought in Karakalpakstan alone. Of the 116 thousand crops harvested in July, only 15 thousand hectares were saved. And in the Khorezm region in the same year, he harvested 65 thousand hectares!

Taking into account that the factor of concern for environmental safety is of great importance for Uzbekistan and for the Central Asian region as a whole, our Government and

the state pay great attention to environmental protection and rational use of natural resources when adopting legal documents aimed at improving the state of the natural environment.

Ecology on a massive scale is one of the problems of our time. The issues related to solving the problem of ecology in the circle of universal human problems remaining in the whirlpool of humanity are becoming particularly relevant. The first President of our Country, I.A.Karimov, in his work "Uzbekistan in the future of the 21st century: ensuring security, stability conditions and guarantees of progress" notes: "All of humanity, the population of our country, has faced a huge environmental risk in a scheme that has been going on for a century. Not noticing this, sitting and clapping your hands is tantamount to condemning yourself to death. Unfortunately, many people still treat this problem carelessly and irresponsibly." [1,112]

Since the environmental problem is directly related to human activity, its solution has largely become a link with family education. The structural organization of the family, Salvation, the pedigree of young people who lead Kadam into independent life, their talent will find its vivid expression in the image of children who will have a unique worldview in Ham.

Social responsibility to society for Sissi children plays an extremely important role in solving an environmental problem, in addition to the fact that they can associate their personal interests with social ones, that is, with the interests of society. In other words, a positive solution to an environmental problem is determined by the stage of development of environmental thinking, consciousness, values, worldview, attitude to the environment, and people's responsibility. This issue is directly related to the family in which people become adults. Therefore, uchi, understanding the family as a sacred gift, attaches special importance to functioning in accordance with it.

The upbringing and bringing of a harmonious generation to perfection begins with the family. A person cannot imagine his life without a family, and in this environment he matures as a member of society. The atmosphere of upbringing in the family depends on the culture of family relations. The responsibility of parents for the upbringing of children, the exemplary order established in the family, and positive traditions are the subtle facets of the culture of family relations. The spirituality of the child is formed in the family, that is, a moral outlook, ideas about good and evil, duty and responsibility appear.

"Speaking of the family," says the first president of our independent state, Islam Karimov, "it is difficult for us to admit that, first of all, the family is a hearth of education that preserves the eternity of life, our sacred customs, but at the same time has a direct impact on how future generations will grow up as people" [2,448].

In order to interpret the prestige of this status in accordance with the requirements of the time, based on the high status of the family in the decision-making process in an environmentally sustainable society, attention should be paid to: firstly, natural and social factors; secondly, progressive traditions and styles in it; thirdly, spiritual. to the state of education and, fourthly, to moral, aesthetic, legal, environmental and labor education in the family.

In a person who embodies a sense of environmental responsibility, biological and social factors must dictate to each other. The cornerstone of environmental education is to attract the child's attention to the beauties of special nature from an early age, focusing on the flora

and fauna of nature, talking about the reserves of existing natural resources, their present and future. Parents decide for themselves how to instill in their children a culture of rational use of natural resources in a family environment..

References:

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3. A great and holy, independent homeland. Popular science brochure. - T., 2011..